

Graph Deep Learning in Species Distribution Models: a Spatial Simulation

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Abstract

Species distribution models (SDMs) are crucial in many ecological applications such as biodiversity conservation, invasion biology and global change ecology. State-of-the-art deep learning SDM methods allow for modelling multiple species jointly, can learn complex & non-linear responses and take the spatial context into account. However, they require point data or a fixed grid structure and only limitedly consider landscape configuration. By representing the model's covariates as a graph (i.e. network structure) consisting of nodes and edges, we applied graph deep learning models in SDM simulations. For each node, the information from a non-fixed number of neighbours can be aggregated, up to several “hops” away. Our results suggest that these models can learn adjacency effects, and improve predictive performance of SDMs. By integrating features related to dispersal and the spatial configuration of the landscape, graph deep learning allows for better insights in species distributions and improved starting points for downstream tasks.

Keywords: species distribution models, graph deep learning, landscape networks

1. Introduction

Species distribution models (SDMs) are popular tools among ecologists to model the distribution of species (Elith & Leathwick 2009). Based on environmental predictors (also called covariates) such as temperature and precipitation, SDMs are able to predict habitat suitability in geographical space. These spatial distribution outputs have many applications, for example, in

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

guiding conservation (e.g. Guisan et al. 2013) or monitoring invasive species (e.g. Fenollosa et al. 2025). Currently, traditional methods, such as Random Forests (RF), are being extended by deep learning methods, which benefit from major improvements in algorithms, hardware and large datasets (e.g. Larcher et al. 2024). These deep learning methods allow for modelling multiple species simultaneously, and can capture complex effects to explain species distributions (Brun et al. 2024, Hu et al. 2025).

The large majority of SDM methods, including deep learning methods such as multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), is, however, point- or pixel-based: these models only consider single points (tabular data) as an input, or pixels in a fixed grid structure (e.g. remote sensing imagery). In the case of point-based spatial methods, no spatial context can be derived, unless explicitly added, whereas for CNNs, the contextual information is present, but limited to the fixed, gridded structure (Frazier & Song 2024). A more flexible structure can be provided by graphs (networks). Within a graph representation, each data point or node can be connected by an edge to a non-fixed number of other data points, being the node's neighbours.

The inclusion of graphs in deep learning and the development of graph deep learning algorithms have recently led to many successful applications (Zhou et al. 2020). Although graph theory is already well integrated in ecology, especially for representing habitat networks (Foltête et al. 2012) and species communities (Thuiller et al. 2024) or trophic networks (Delmas et al. 2019), graph neural networks (GNNs) have only very recently entered the SDM community (Harrell et al. 2025, Wu et al. 2025), and their potential remains largely unexplored. Many species distributions can, however, be expected to be influenced by the landscape structure and habitat patch configuration. One can think of various neighbourhood-dependent effects (neighbouring habitats, anthropogenic disturbances, food sources) that may affect distributions (e.g. Ortiz-Rodríguez et al. 2019, Collart et al. 2025), for different degrees of species mobility. The variables relevant for explaining these effects may not always be informative at the location of a node of interest itself, but rather at the location of its neighbours. Passing information between neighbouring nodes is thus crucial when these effects apply.

With this study, we aim to illustrate the potential of graph deep learning for species distribution models within a simulated context, where presences and absences for each node not only depend on local covariate values, but also on the value of one covariate of the neighbours. We hypothesized that a non-spatial MLP or RF would fail to accurately predict presences and absences, as these cannot use any links between nodes. On the other hand, a GNN was expected to perform better due to its intrinsic model architecture, which also requires edge information to represent connections between the data points.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Graph Convolutional Layers

Graph convolutional layers, the building blocks of GNNs, can be considered a generalization of convolutional layers on grids in CNNs. While CNNs require a fixed input structure, there is no such requirement for graph convolutional layers, where each node can have any number of neighbours in an arbitrary order (Bronstein et al. 2017). Within such a layer, information from

neighbouring nodes is collected and aggregated for each individual (focal) node simultaneously. In a first step, a message is calculated for each neighbour. The message calculation functions can optionally make use of edge attributes (which may for example represent the length of the shared border between two habitat patches), or can weigh variables or the message itself by edge weights. Secondly, all messages are propagated along the edges, after which the messages of all neighbouring nodes are aggregated (e.g. by simple averaging). Lastly, in the update step, the aggregated messages are combined with the focal node's own information. The functions for message calculations, aggregation and updating have few constraints, and their parameters are shared across all nodes. These flexible convolutions should thus also enable capturing neighbourhood-based effects in SDMs.

2.2. Simulation of the Graph Data

We applied GNNs, MLPs and RFs to the distributions of 45 simulated, fictitious species, with for each a simple adjacency effect included, where habitat suitability values were affected by one of the covariates of the neighbouring nodes (*Figure 1a*). In a first step, a graph was created by triangulating 2000 nodes with random coordinates and randomly removing 40 % of the edges. Next, each node was assigned five covariates, where each covariate varied differently across space. A single attribute was added to each edge, randomly chosen from the $[0, 1[$ interval. When starting off from (segmented) grid data to create the graph's structure, one could represent each spatial unit as a node, and aggregate all covariates based on their overlap (*Figure 1b*). Besides predefined covariates, the node and edge attributes could be extended by geometric properties, such as the spatial units' area or circumference, or the length or orientation of the edges.

Figure 1. a) In this simulation, graph structures were created by triangulation of random points. The final presences & absences were simulated by combining all covariates x_i via a partial response s_i for each covariate i . An adjacency effect was added, increasing or decreasing suitability values for nodes with specific neighbours. Final suitability values were thresholded to presences & absences. b) When using real-world data, a graph's structure could be derived from a meaningful variable which can be represented as an area of contiguous segments. In this case, each node represents a segment, and the edges link nodes corresponding to spatially adjacent segments. c) The cross-validation approach made use of five training & validation graphs, and one held-out test graph. d) A cross-validation procedure was applied for selecting the best-performing GNN & MLP model architectures or the best RF hyperparameters. Predictions on the held-out graph were used for comparing performance.

Finally, these individual covariates were processed to produce a final suitability per node: Each covariate was rescaled, and converted to a partial response by applying a set of functions (e.g. hyperbolic, composite). The initial suitability per node was then calculated as a weighted sum of these partial responses with random weights from the interval $[0, 1[$. All partial response functions and weights were unique per species. In addition, each node was randomly assigned a categorical class “A”, “B” or “C” (e.g. land cover). Each node of the class “B” increased the suitability of neighbouring nodes of the classes “A” by the value of the corresponding edge attribute, while the suitability was decreased for neighbours of class “C”. This could be considered an example of positive and negative effects, such as pollution, disturbance or fertilization from neighbouring land cover areas on habitat suitability values, mediated by the edge. This effect was added to the weighted sum with its own weight, which varied per 15 species. A weight of 0 indicated no effect, whereas for a weight of 1.5, the effect moderately contributed to the final suitability, and for a weight of 10, the response variable was dominated by the adjacency effect. The result was min-max-scaled. The final presences and absences were determined by thresholding with a value of 0.75.

2.3. Model Selection and Comparison

A cross-validation procedure (*Figure 1d*) was used to select the best model architecture from a range of proposed architectures. All architectures included at least one graph attention (GAT) layer, which was replaced by a fully connected linear layer in the MLP architectures to keep the number of trainable parameters comparable. The RF models were finetuned by varying the maximum depth (no max., 5, 10 or 15) and the maximum features (square root, log2 or the number of features). Per species, six graphs were created, where the spatial distribution of the covariates differed, but all responses were identically constructed. Each of the first five training graphs represented a different cross-validation fold, while the sixth graph was held out for testing (*Figure 1c*).

3. Results and Discussion

Our results suggest that the best GNNs indeed perform better overall compared to the best MLP and RF models within this simulated context. Performance metrics were compared using a beta generalized linear mixed model and post hoc test. On average, the GNNs’ area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC_{ROC}), sharpness ($1 - 2 \times$ the square root of $(p \times (1 - p))$ with p the predicted probability) and $1 - RMSE$ on the test data significantly ($\alpha=0.05$) exceeded the AUC_{ROC} , sharpness and $1 - RMSE$ of the MLPs and RFs for the effect weights of 1.5 and 10.0 (*Figure 2*). The calibration error for the GNNs only significantly differed from the calibration error for the MLPs for the effect weights > 0 , but was not significantly different compared to the RFs.

Despite the overall divergence in performance between models, the individual models of all types still displayed a rather large variability in performance for different effect sizes. This could likely be attributed to variability between runs, where in each run, a varying number of nodes were affected by the adjacency effect. Additionally, this influenced the prevalence (class imbalance), which in turn likely affected the performance of all models.

Figure 2. AUC_{ROC}, 1 - calibration error, sharpness and 1 - RMSE compared between the three model types, for different adjacency effect weights. The whiskers indicate the confidence intervals. All metrics range between 0 and 1, and higher values indicate better predictive performance. Bars sharing a letter do not significantly differ for the given effect weight (0.0, 1.5 or 10.0).

Besides this example adjacency effect, a broad range of other ecological effects could be represented in GNNs, such as food sources, disturbances, the availability of nesting/foraging areas nearby, or patches that prevent a species' dispersal. In multiple cases, several graph convolutional layers may be required to capture effects over a longer distance away from the focal node (i.e. multiple node "hops").

4. Conclusion

Our results indicate that graph deep learning could indeed be used to capture neighbour-based effects, whereas regular MLPs or RF models lack the spatial connections to do so. By using graphs, the landscape can be represented more conceptually, capturing longer-distance relationships at a chosen scale. Future SDM case studies should, however, evaluate the potential in a real-world setting for species that are expected to be affected by such neighbourhood effects. Furthermore, graph deep learning could additionally be integrated into SDMs for representing species interactions in communities, allowing the integration of species-specific traits (Wu et al. 2025) or phylogeny into the model.

Funding

This work was supported by the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO) [1166125N].

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